

The Oxidation of Sulphur Dioxide in the Electrodeless Discharge.

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Priestley ("Experiments and observations on different kinds of air," Birmingham, 1790, 2, 323) found that sulphur dioxide is decomposed by electric sparks. Buff and Hoffmann (*Annalen*, 1860, 113, 129) showed that sulphur and sulphur trioxide are formed by the sparking of sulphur dioxide and that sulphur trioxide is formed when a mixture of sulphur dioxide with half its volume of oxygen is exposed to the discharge. De Wilde (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 256) and Poliakoff (*Mag. Chim. Cath. Katerinoslav.*, 1926, 207) obtained similar results with the silent electric discharge. Deville (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1865, 53, 366) stated that a state of equilibrium is reached which prevents the completion of the reaction, but that if sulphur trioxide is removed as fast as it is formed by absorption with concentrated sulphuric acid or water, the reaction may proceed to completion. Berthelot (*Ann. chim. Phys.*, 1898, vii, 14, 167, 289) said that some platinum sulphide may be formed on the platinum electrodes. According to Poliakoff the oxidation of sulphur dioxide is more or less completely dependent on the concentration, pressure, etc. If oxygen alone is subjected to the action of the discharge, it will unite with sulphur dioxide when removed from the influence of the discharge. Sulphur dioxide is, however, not so activated.

Henry and Wolf (*J. Phys. Radium*, 1920, 10, 81) believe that the emission spectrum of sulphur dioxide produced by an oscillating discharge is attributable to the production of sulphur monoxide.

The action of the electrodeless discharge in producing chemical changes has been the subject of investigation in these laboratories (Bhatnagar, Sharma and Mitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 379; Mahant, *ibid.*, 1929, 6, 705; Yajnik, Sharma and Bhatnagar *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 148, 394) and the present communicat

contains the results of a study of this source of excitation on the oxidation of sulphur dioxide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The apparatus used in the present investigation is shown in the diagram. The aspirator A and the connecting tube upto stop-cock S_8 and S_9 were evacuated by connecting to the vacuum pump through the stop-cocks S_1 , S_2 , S_3 , and S_4 . Stop-cock S_2 was then closed and sulphur dioxide led into aspirator by opening the stop-cock S_8 , till the required pressure was indicated by the manometer M_1 . This was then closed and oxygen allowed to enter through the stop-cock S_9 till the manometer indicated no vacuum. Stop-cock S_3 was then closed and the gases allowed to diffuse into one another for 2 hours. The ratio of the gases in the mixture was calculated from the partial pressures as recorded by means of the manometer.

At the end of this interval, the discharge tube system was connected to the vacuum pump and evacuated. The mixture was then allowed to leak into the discharge tube through the stop-cock S_3 via the cocks S_4 , S_5 , and S_6 (the tube to S_8 and S_9 having been disconnected) while the discharge was allowed to pass for 5 hours. The rate of leakage of the gas into the system was regulated by means of the stop-cock S_3 . The mixture of gases was passed through a trap T_1 (immersed in ice) and then through a bubbler B containing a strong solution of caustic soda as it emerged out of the discharge tube. The pressure, at which the discharge was allowed to pass,

was 5-10 mm. and the system was evacuated from time to time to maintain this vacuum.

After the exposure the stop-cock S_3 was closed and S_2 loosened to allow air to sweep the tubes. The discharge tube was disconnected and well washed with water. The bubbler B was also well washed and both the washings mixed. The sulphite and sulphate contents were estimated and from this the percentage of oxidised sulphur dioxide was calculated.

The apparatus for the production of the electrodeless discharge has already been described (*cf.* Bhatnagar, Shrivastava, Mathur and Sharma, *Phil. Mag.*, 1928, **52**, 1226).

Preliminary investigations showed that only sulphate and sulphite were present in solution after exposure. No thionates could be detected except possibly in the case of pure sulphur dioxide when a yellowish precipitate was obtained with $Hg(NO_3)_2$ but no precipitate was obtained with $HgCl_2$ or $AgNO_3$ and no decolorisation could be noticed with $KMnO_4$. Free sulphur in a state of fine division was found to be sticking to the sides of the discharge tube when pure sulphur dioxide was subjected to the influence of the discharge and a drop of mercury in the discharge tube acquired a black coating of HgS . When the discharge was passed through a mixture of SO_2 and oxygen, a drop of mercury in the discharge tube formed a white coating which gave tests showing that a sulphate of mercury had formed.

Effect of the discharge on mixtures of different compositions.—Mixtures of different compositions were made by varying the ratio of the gases mixed in the aspirator and the effect of the discharge on these was studied. The results are given Table I.

TABLE I.

Composition ($SO_2 : O_2$)	...	50 : 50	60 : 40	70 : 30	80 : 20	100 : 0
SO_2 oxidised (%)	...	25.5	{ 29.55 35.79 40.23	{ 23.37 22.94 25.69	{ 19.86 17.08 19.28	{ 5.26 3.68 3.94

Influence of change of frequency on the percentage of sulphur dioxide oxidised.—The frequency of the oscillations from the secondary of the Tesla coil can be varied by varying the capacity in the circuit. To study the effect of change of frequency, the capacity in

the circuit was varied in the following way: In the first two experiments, two and four plates of the condenser were connected and in the last two experiments two and four plates from a similar condenser were connected in parallel with the 4 plates of the first condenser. A mixture of 80% SO_2 and 40% oxygen was used in this investigation. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

No. of plates	2	4	6	8
Approx. capacity (microfarads)	22.4	67.2	89.6	134.4
SO_2 oxidised (%)	33.23	85.79	37.62	34.08

Influence of mercury.—During the course of the investigation mercury leaked into the discharge tube in some experiments in which the Hg seal stop-cock had been accidentally left loose. It was noticed in these cases that the percentage of sulphur dioxide oxidised was much greater. Careful analysis showed that though part of this increase was due to the precipitation of mercurous chloride along with the barium sulphate in the estimation, some of it was really due to some sort of catalytic effect of mercury. A regular investigation of this was undertaken and mixture of different compositions exposed to the discharge in the presence of mercury. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Composition ($\text{SO}_2 : \text{O}_2$) ...	60 : 40	70 : 30	80 : 20
SO_2 oxidised (%) ...	{ 46.53 51.11	{ 42.73 35.18	{ 30.57 35.82

Spectrographic study.—To elucidate the mechanism of the reaction, a spectral study of the discharge produced in the system was undertaken. The discharge tube employed for this purpose was the same as used for a study of oxygen in the electrodeless discharge and the arrangement of the apparatus altered to suit the requirements. Spectra of the glow produced in pure sulphur dioxide, sulphur dioxide in the presence of mercury, sulphur dioxide and oxygen as mixture, sulphur dioxide and oxygen in the presence of mercury, and of mercury in vacuum were taken on a Hilger E3 quartz spectrograph, Ilford special rapid panchromatic plates being used for photographing the spectra.

The mercury resonance line at 2536.7 \AA was not detected on the plates.

Discussion.

The results indicate that the maximum amount of sulphur dioxide is oxidised when the mixture has a composition of 60% sulphur dioxide and 40% oxygen. This may be compared to the 66% sulphur dioxide and 33% oxygen mixture which Buff and Hoffmann (*loc. cit.*) found was slowly converted into sulphur trioxide when subjected to the spark discharge. Coehen and Becker (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1919, 70, 88) showed that on illumination by ultraviolet light the reaction $2 \text{SO}_2 + \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons 2 \text{SO}_3$ is in equilibrium when about 100% of the sulphur trioxide has been formed, whereas in the light of a mercury lamp the equilibrium is reached when about 65% of the sulphur trioxide has been formed. They also showed that the equilibrium constant is independent of the proportions of sulphur dioxide and oxygen in the mixture and of the temperature.

The results on the influence of change of frequency do not show much change in the percentage of sulphur dioxide oxidised, the variations in the results being within the limits of experimental error. This is in agreement with the results of Hunt and Schumb (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 3152) on the effect of the electrodeless discharge on carbon dioxide. These authors did not find any appreciable variation in the percentage of decomposition when the wave-length of the discharge was changed from 51 to 34 metres.

Aqueous solutions of sulphur dioxide are known to be slowly oxidised to sulphuric acid with the precipitation of sulphur. Thiosulphuric and polythionic acids are also known to be formed in the course of the autoxidation. (*cf* Mellor, "Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry." London, Vol. X, p. 207). The absence of these thiosulphates and polythionates in the products of the reaction due to the electrodeless discharge shows that the mechanism of the process is not akin to autoxidation. According to Coehen (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1907, 21, 545) the photochemical decomposition of sulphur dioxide furnishes sulphur and oxygen, the latter being largely used up to form sulphur trioxide. Hill (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1924, 20, 107) believes that the primary process involves either a dissociation of the sulphur dioxide molecule into atomic sulphur and molecular oxygen or simply an activation of the sulphur dioxide molecule so that the final result in either case is $3 \text{SO}_2 = 2 \text{SO}_3 + \text{S}$.

As already stated, Poliakoff (*loc. cit.*) has shown that if oxygen alone is subjected to the influence of the silent electric discharge, it will unite with sulphur dioxide even when removed from the influence of the discharge. Sulphur dioxide is however not so activated.

The general similarity of the spectra of the glow of sulphur dioxide and of mixtures of sulphur dioxide and oxygen shows that pure sulphur dioxide is first decomposed into oxygen and sulphur when subjected to the electrodeless discharge. The activated oxygen then combines with sulphur dioxide to give sulphur trioxide. In the case of mixtures of sulphur dioxide and oxygen, the oxygen alone is activated and combines with sulphur dioxide. It cannot be definitely said at present if the activation of oxygen is due to the formation of ozone or due to an activation of the molecule of oxygen as such. According to Hunt and Schumb (*loc. cit.*) there is no change of pressure when oxygen is exposed to the electrodeless discharge and hence no ozone is formed. This aspect of the question is under investigation and will be discussed in a separate communication.

The exact rôle of mercury in increasing the percentage of sulphur dioxide is also being investigated.

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